

Proof of Near-square Primes Problem

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Abstract

There are infinitely many primes which are of the form in near-square.

1 Introduction

The number of near-square primes problem is as following[Iwaniec(1978)]:

Are there infinitely many primes which are of the form $p = n^2 + 1$ for integer n ?

2 Proof

By definition, n^2 is an even number. By definition of generalized prime number sequence[Yoon(2023a)]:

$$p_1 = (t^3 + 3t^2 + 2t)p_2 + p_3$$

Note that p_n ($n \in \mathbb{N}$) is an arbitrary prime number that is in prime number sequence. And with Goldbach's conjecture[Yoon(2023b)], $n^2 + 1 := p_4 + p_5 + 1$:

$$n = \sqrt{p - 1} = \sqrt{p_6 + p_7} = 2^x \sqrt{p_8 + p_9 + 1} \quad (x \in \mathbb{N})$$

This implies there is any odd number takes square form that can be expressed into the sum of two primes plus one, then there are infinite number of primes in form of $n^2 + 1$. With Goldbach's conjecture being true, the number of near-square primes is infinite.

3 More Explanation

$$n^2 + 1 = 2^{2x}(p_8 + p_9 + 1) + 1$$

The conjecture gets true with definition of generalized prime number sequence with arbitrary p_8, p_9 [Yoon(2023a)].

$$M_n = n(n + 1)(n + 2)$$

$$\implies \forall p \geq 3 \implies p = k + \alpha_1 M_1 + \alpha_2 M_2 + \alpha_3 M_3 \cdots \quad (\forall \alpha \in \mathbb{P} \cup \{0, 1\}, k \in \{0, 1, 3, 5\})$$

The case fits the condition of generalized prime number sequence.

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